

Conservation of energy, a juridical review

Abstract

Albert Einstein, along with the majority of physicists, believed that energy cannot ever be destroyed. This is quite a counterintuitive concept. After all, if 1,000 joules of energy are expended in performing 1,000 joules worth of work, by bending, twisting, crushing, or breaking some object, for instance, or simply by moving it from one place to another, then the energy has surely been used up and no longer exists. Nevertheless, this idea has been canonized as the law of conservation of energy and forms an integral part of the first law of thermodynamics. Why do physicists believe it and is there any truth in it?

Why do physicists believe that energy cannot be destroyed?

The origins of the idea are generally attributed to the works of **Ludwig August Colding** (13 July 1815 – 21 March 1888), **James Prescott Joule** (24 December 1818 – 11 October 1889) and **René Descartes** (31 March 1596 – 11 February 1650)

Colding was of the opinion that, *“just as it is true that the human soul is immortal, so it must also surely be a general law of nature that the forces of nature are imperishable.”*

Joule stated: *“Believing that the power to destroy belongs to the Creator alone I affirm ... that any theory which, when carried out, demands the annihilation of force (the 19th century term for energy), is necessarily erroneous.”*

Descartes:- *“God... in the beginning created matter along with motion and rest, and now, through His ordinary concourse alone, conserves just as much motion and rest in the whole of it as He put there at that time.”*

In each case the reasoning seems to lack a certain scientific rigor.

Others, including **Émilie Du Châtelet**, **Hermann von Helmholtz** and **Julius Robert von Mayer** demonstrated that some forms of energy are equivalent to other forms, but did not demonstrate that energy is always conserved

Now it is true that, in many cases, when work is done, the energy does change from one form to another. If we use mechanical energy to raise an object off the ground, for example, the object gains a similar amount of potential energy. If we later allow the object to fall, then as it loses potential energy it gains kinetic energy that can be used to turn a wheel, giving us back some mechanical energy with which we could again raise a weight off the ground, even if that mechanical energy is much less than we started with.

But that is not true in every case. It is certainly assumed, when there appears to have been a loss of energy in some practical situation, such as when two cars collide, that all of the “missing” kinetic energy must simply have been converted into some other form, such as heat or noise or vibration and that it must still exist somewhere. In such a chaotic model though, it is difficult to calculate or measure the energies involved so it remains an assumption.

Can energy be destroyed?

To simplify and clarify the essentials, we can consider the following closed system.

A one litre tank contains 10 litres of air compressed to 10 bar, both air and tank being at room temperature (e.g. 10 degrees C.). The 1 litre tank is connected by a valve to an evacuated 9 litre tank, which is also at room temperature.

We therefore have some potential energy in the form of compressed air in the small tank, which we could use to perform work, and some in the form of the vacuum in the second tank, which could also, in theory, perform work, e.g. sucking up dust, plus some (room temperature) heat energy in the tanks and their contents.

We open the valve, allowing the air to fill all the available space in both tanks.

We are now left with 10 litres of air at near normal atmospheric pressure.

Where has the potential energy gone?

All the air and both tanks will also be at a temperature much lower than their original temperatures.

Where has the heat energy gone?

All the potential energy has been used up in performing the work of expanding the compressed gas, along with much of the heat energy. They no longer exist in any form, and no part of the system is capable of performing any further work.

Every mechanic will be familiar with the ice that forms at the valve when draining a compressed air tank at the end of the day. If we apply the van der Waals equation -- the mathematical formula that describes the behaviour of real gases with respect to pressure, volume, number of molecules, and temperature – we find that the temperature of the air leaving the first tank falls by over 40 degrees centigrade as the pressure falls from 10 bar to 1 bar. [1]

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=yLuNPTxLTGs>

In theoretical physics, however, there is also the concept of an imaginary “ideal” gas. The ideal gas laws make calculations very simple, but the results are hopelessly inaccurate and misleading. In the above case for instance they would conclude that the final temperature of the air remains unchanged at 10 degrees C., rather than falling to minus 32 degrees C as it would do in the real world.

If real gases behaved like “ideal” gases of course, then refrigerators, freezers and air conditioners wouldn’t work. Nevertheless, even under the ideal gas laws, all the potential energy of the compressed air in the demonstration above is “destroyed” as its pressure falls to normal atmospheric pressure, the vacuum also disappears and there is no corresponding increase in heat or any other form of energy either inside or outside the system so it can no longer perform any kind of work.

Can other forms of energy be destroyed?

Some energy is lost whenever energy is used to perform work. If this were not so, then every machine could potentially function as a perpetual motion.

It is quite easy to demonstrate experimentally that energy is lost whenever energy is converted from one form to another, that energy is lost whenever energy is transferred from one body to another and energy is lost whenever there is a change of vector, polarity, pressure or any of several other attributes of energy.

Simple observation and calculation can show that noise, friction, heat, air resistance etc. cannot account for these losses. One simple, easily reproducible demonstration comprises a coil spring repeatedly compressed and released inside a closed container. The amount of energy required to compress the spring is easily established and if that energy could not be destroyed then the temperature of the spring and the air in the container would rise steadily at a rate that is equally simple to calculate. No such increase in temperature is observed. All the energy expended in compressing the spring thousands of times simply ceases to exist.

In other simple, everyday observations, such as bouncing balls or the colliding spheres in a Newton's cradle or a simple pendulum swinging, we can watch kinetic energy rapidly dissipate in a matter of seconds.

Entropy

In thermodynamics, dissipation is the result of *“an irreversible process that affects a thermodynamic system in which energy transforms from an initial form to a final form, where the capacity of the final form to do thermodynamic work is less than that of the initial form”*.

Since the definition of energy is the capacity to do work, then if there is less capacity to do work, then energy, by definition, must have been destroyed, which brings us to the second law of thermodynamics.

The second law is based on observation rather than religious faith and is usually stated in words to the effect that *“in any energy transfer or transformation, **the total entropy of an isolated system can never decrease over time**”*. In simple terms, that just means that energy cannot be created -- which we already knew from the first law.

To avoid the obvious, but unstated, implication that the entropy can **increase** – i.e. energy can be destroyed -- the second law has been rephrased in many different ways, often using concepts like “disorderliness” to define the central concept of entropy instead of “energy loss”.

In addition we are faced with a host of variations on the theme, including negative entropy, excess entropy, system entropy, total entropy, thermodynamic entropy, maximum entropy, statistical entropy, zero entropy, conditional entropy, relative entropy, Holevo entropy, quantum entropy, conditional quantum entropy, Shannon entropy and von Neumann entropy.

The result is general confusion.

“The entropy of the universe tends to a maximum.” – Rudolf Clausius (1865)

“The Entropy of the Universe tends to zero.” – Peter Guthrie Tait (1868) [2]

“There are almost as many formulations of The Second Law as there have been discussions of it.” -- Percy Williams Bridgman (1941)

“Whoever uses the term 'entropy' in a discussion always wins since no one knows what entropy really is.” – John von Neumann (194?)

Discussion

Repealing the law of conservation of energy would rationalise a great deal of elementary Newtonian physics. It would mean that the very useful concept of negative energy would not be restricted to calculations involving gravity: since a lot of energy is lost to inertia, then inertia could be quantified in units of joules rather than kilograms and how inertia varies with the square of the velocity could be determined empirically and formularised: kinetic energy could correctly be considered a vector quantity and treated as such, with negative values in elastic collisions where applicable, and entropy, measured in joules, would simply represent how much energy is lost in any energy transfer or transformation, as it was originally conceived.

Conclusion

The first law of thermodynamics should be revised to reflect the fact that energy can in fact be destroyed and the law of conservation of energy should be revoked.

[1]. Using the Van der Waals equation for air to find T_2 when T_1 is 10 degrees C., V_1 is 1 litre and P_1 is 10 bar if V_2 is 10 litres and P_2 is 1 bar.

$$\left(P + \frac{a}{V_m^2}\right) (V_m - b) = RT$$

Where:

- P is the pressure (in bar),
- V_m is the molar volume (in L/mol),
- T is the temperature (in K),
- R is the gas constant (we'll use $R = 0.08314 \text{ L}\cdot\text{bar}/\text{mol}\cdot\text{K}$),
- a and b are van der Waals constants for air.

Van der Waals constants for air:

- $a = 1.36 \text{ L}^2\cdot\text{bar}/\text{mol}^2$
- $b = 0.0365 \text{ L}/\text{mol}$

$$T_2 \approx 241 \text{ K or } -32^\circ\text{C}$$

[2] Peter Guthrie Tait, *Sketch of Thermodynamics* (Edinburgh, 1968), P.29